

Novel Low-Complexity SWIPT Precoding Schemes

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Abstract—Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) represents an enabling paradigm for future energy-sustainable networks. Multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technology enhances the performance of SWIPT systems via precoding. We typically rely on heuristic precoding designs in practice, due to their favorable performance-complexity balance, as opposed to their optimization-based counterparts. On the other hand, these designs provide limited flexibility. Furthermore, the standard precoding heuristics are SWIPT-agnostic. In this paper, we propose a novel MIMO precoding framework for SWIPT that is based on the notion of controllable residual interference to resolve the aforementioned issues. Specifically, we consider a multiple-input single-output (MISO) broadcast system for SWIPT with separate energy and information receivers. In this context, we formulate interference-constrained problems and apply a relaxation to obtain low-complexity solutions that admit closed-form expressions. We also extend our approach to hybrid precoding designs for the case where the base station adopts an analog/digital architecture due to particularly stringent cost and energy consumption constraints. Numerical simulations unveil the performance gains of the proposed precoding schemes over the solutions based on semi-definite relaxation (SDR) and heuristic baseline methods and provide valuable insights.

Index Terms—Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer, hybrid precoding, interference-constrained optimization, semi-definite relaxation, harmonic mean relaxation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) integrates radio communication with wireless charging to prolong the lifetime of energy-constrained terminals, such as Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices [1]. Multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technology, which leverages multiple antennas at the base station (BS), enhances the performance of the SWIPT paradigm via transmit precoding [2], [3].

In many scenarios of practical interest, such as indoor deployments, the BSs are subject to particularly stringent cost and energy consumption constraints. The adoption of an analog/digital (A/D) transceiver architecture has been proposed as a cost-effective and energy-efficient solution for approaching the performance of a fully-digital (FD) implementation that has a larger number of radio frequency (RF) chains [4]. This concept, which has been borrowed by the millimeter-wave massive MIMO communication regime, is based on the use of a low-dimensional digital baseband precoder (DBP) and a high-dimensional analog RF precoder (RFP). The latter is commonly realized with the aid of phase shifters.

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Regardless of the BS type, *optimization-based precoding designs commonly impose a prohibitive computational burden* (especially in massive MIMO settings). Consequently, linear precoding heuristics are typically employed in practice, since they strike a favorable balance between performance and complexity. Nevertheless, the conventional precoding heuristics [5], such as maximum ratio (MR) and zero forcing (ZF) or regularized ZF (RZF) precoding, *have not been devised having in mind the rate-energy trade-off that characterizes SWIPT systems*. Furthermore, SWIPT-aware precoding heuristics, such as the parametric MR/ZF precoding scheme proposed in [2] and the adaptation of signal-to-leakage-plus-noise-ratio (SLNR) precoding presented in [6], *provide limited design flexibility in meeting predefined performance criteria and constraints*. The same holds true for the heuristic hybrid precoder (HP) designs found in the literature [7]–[9].

The SWIPT-aware FD precoder (FDP) heuristics mentioned above *leave unaffected a desirable amount of residual interference to control the fundamental rate-energy trade-off*. Moreover, it is well known that the optimal combiner in multi-user MIMO systems is given in closed-form as the solution of a *generalized Rayleigh quotient maximization problem*. Motivated by these facts, we propose a *novel precoding framework for MIMO SWIPT systems that addresses the aforementioned issues*. Specifically, we consider a multi-user multiple-input single-output (MISO) system with separated information decoding and energy harvesting receivers (IDR/EHR). When an A/D BS architecture is utilized, we apply a singular-value decomposition (SVD)-based RFP design to reduce the complexity. Influenced by the design approach in [10], which however does not consider neither SWIPT nor HP, we formulate a variety of FDP/DBP interference-constrained optimization problems, present their semi-definite relaxation (SDR)-based solutions, and derive low-complexity alternatives via harmonic mean relaxations (HMR), which allow us to transform the original optimization problems into generalized eigenvalue problems and obtain FDP/DBP designs with closed-form expressions. Numerical simulations unveil the performance gains of the proposed precoding methods over optimization-based and baseline heuristic precoding schemes and provide valuable insights.

II. SYSTEM AND CHANNEL MODELS

The considered system consists of a set $\mathcal{K}_I \triangleq \{1, \dots, K_I\}$ of IDRs, another set $\mathcal{K}_E \triangleq \{1, \dots, K_E\}$ of EHRs, and a BS, as shown in Fig. 1. Each receiver is equipped with a single antenna, while the BS has a set $\mathcal{M} \triangleq \{1, \dots, M\}$ of antennas and a set $\mathcal{L} \triangleq \{1, \dots, L\}$ of RF chains, where $L \geq K \triangleq K_I + K_E$ and $L = M$ or $L < M$ depending on whether a FD or A/D architecture is adopted, respectively. Throughout the

Fig. 1. System setup.

paper, we address the members of these sets via the indexes $i, k \in \mathcal{K}_I$, $j, n \in \mathcal{K}_E$, $m \in \mathcal{M}$, and $l \in \mathcal{L}$, respectively, unless it is explicitly indicated otherwise. The BS serves the users on a single time-frequency resource by employing linear precoding and assigning a separate information/energy beam to each IDR/EHR, respectively.

We consider quasi-static, frequency-flat Rician fading channels. We denote by $\mathbf{h}_i \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and $\mathbf{g}_j \in \mathbb{C}^M$ the baseband equivalent channels from the BS to IDR i and EHR j , respectively. The BS-IDR i channel is expressed as $\mathbf{h}_i = \sqrt{\beta_i} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\kappa}{1+\kappa}} \bar{\mathbf{h}}_i + \sqrt{\frac{1}{1+\kappa}} \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_i \right)$, where $\beta_i = L_p(d_i) X_{sf}$ denotes the large-scale fading coefficient, $L_p(d_i) = C_0 \left(\frac{d_i}{d_0} \right)^{-\alpha}$ is the path loss at propagation distance d_i , C_0 corresponds to the path loss at a reference distance of $d_0 = 1$ m in the far-field of the BS, α stands for the path loss exponent, $X_{sf} = 10^{x_{sf}/10}$ with $x_{sf} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{sf}^2)$ refers to the shadow fading, κ denotes the Rician factor, $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_i \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is the deterministic line-of-sight (LoS) channel component, and $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_i \in \mathbb{C}^M$ whose elements are $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ random variables corresponds to the Rayleigh fading non-LoS (NLoS) channel component. The BS-EHR j channel is modeled in a similar manner.

1) *Fully-Digital Transmitter*: Under a FD BS implementation, the transmitted signal, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^M$, is given by $\mathbf{x} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i s_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{v}_j e_j$, where $\mathbf{w}_i \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and $\mathbf{v}_j \in \mathbb{C}^M$ denote the precoding vectors assigned to IDR i and EHR j , while $s_i \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ and e_j , which satisfies $\mathbb{E}\{|e_j|^2\} = 1$, represent the information-bearing and energy-carrying signals destined for these users, respectively. Hence, the transmit sum-power is expressed as

$$P_T = \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{x}^\dagger \mathbf{x}\} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{v}_j. \quad (1)$$

Assuming availability of perfect channel state information (CSI) at the BS and the users, the complex baseband received signals at IDR i and EHR j are given by

$$y_i^I = \mathbf{h}_i^\dagger \left(\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_k s_k + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{v}_j e_j \right) + n_i, \quad (2a)$$

$$y_j^E = \mathbf{g}_j^\dagger \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i s_i + \sum_{n \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{v}_n e_n \right) + \nu_j, \quad (2b)$$

where $n_i \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_i^2)$ and $\nu_j \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \delta_j^2)$ denote the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) at these users.

Let us define $\mathbf{R}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ as $\mathbf{R}_i \triangleq \mathbf{h}_i \mathbf{h}_i^\dagger$. Then, assuming that IDR i cannot cancel the interference induced to it by the pseudo-random energy signals, its signal-to-interference-plus-noise-ratio (SINR) is given by

$$\text{SINR}_i = \frac{\mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{w}_i}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \mathbf{w}_k^\dagger \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{w}_k + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{v}_j + \sigma_i^2}. \quad (3)$$

The data rate of this user and the sum-rate of the IDRs, in turn, are written as

$$R_i = \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_i); \quad R = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} R_i. \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, by defining $\mathbf{C}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ as $\mathbf{C}_j \triangleq \mathbf{g}_j \mathbf{g}_j^\dagger$ and ignoring the negligible noise power at EHR j , we express the received RF power at this user as

$$E_j = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{v}_n^\dagger \mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{v}_n + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{w}_i. \quad (5)$$

The harvested direct current (DC) power at EHR j is expressed as $\bar{E}_j = \frac{A_j E_j}{B_j E_j + C_j}$ [11], where $A_j > 0$, $B_j \geq 0$, and C_j are constants that capture the non-linearities of the diodes-based rectifier circuit and are determined via curve-fitting.

2) *A/D Transmitter*: Let's consider a fully-connected A/D structure, wherein each one of the $L < M$ RF chains is connected to the M antennas through M dedicated phase shifters and M shared combiners, thus resulting in ML phase shifters in total, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The HP $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times K}$ is defined as $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{F}_B$, where $\mathbf{F}_R \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times L}$ and $\mathbf{F}_B \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times K}$ denote the RFP and the DBP, respectively. The former is expressed as $\mathbf{F}_R \triangleq [\mathbf{f}_R^{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{f}_R^{(L)}]$, where $\mathbf{f}_R^{(l)} \in \mathbb{C}^M$ represents the l -th analog RF precoding vector and $\mathbf{F}_R(m, l) = \mathbf{f}_R^{(l)}(m) = e^{j\varphi_{m,l}}$ with $\varphi_{m,l} \in [0, 2\pi)$ standing for the value of the phase shifter that connects the m -th BS antenna to the l -th RF chain. The DBP, on the other hand, is expressed as $\mathbf{F}_B \triangleq [\mathbf{f}_1, \dots, \mathbf{f}_{K_I}, \mathbf{t}_1, \dots, \mathbf{t}_{K_E}]$, where $\mathbf{f}_i \in \mathbb{C}^L$ and $\mathbf{t}_j \in \mathbb{C}^L$ correspond to the DB precoding vectors assigned to IDR i and EHR j , respectively. Hence, the transmitted signal is given by $\mathbf{x} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_i s_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{t}_j e_j$.

Thus, the transmit sum-power is expressed as

$$P_T = \mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{x}^\dagger \mathbf{x}\} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{f}_i^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{t}_j^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{t}_j, \quad (6)$$

while the SINR at IDR i is given by

$$\text{SINR}_i = \frac{\mathbf{f}_i^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R^\dagger \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_i}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \mathbf{f}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R^\dagger \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_k + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{t}_j^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R^\dagger \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{t}_j + \sigma_i^2}, \quad (7)$$

and the received RF power at EHR j is written as

$$E_j = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{t}_n^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R^\dagger \mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{t}_n + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{f}_i^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R^\dagger \mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_i. \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2. Fully-connected A/D transmitter structure.

III. PROPOSED LINEAR PRECODING SCHEMES

A. Problem Formulation

1) *Problem I*: We aim at optimizing each information/energy precoding vector, such that the received power of the target IDR/EHR is maximized subject to the interference-power constraints of the other users (IDRs and EHRs) and the transmit power constraint. Assuming a FD BS implementation, the optimization of \mathbf{w}_i is mathematically described as:

$$(P1): \max_{\{\mathbf{w}_i\}} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{w}_i \quad (9a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{R}_k \mathbf{w}_i \leq \xi_k^I, \quad i \neq k, \quad (9b)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{w}_i \geq \xi_j^E, \quad (9c)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i \leq P_i^I, \quad (9d)$$

where $\xi_k^I > 0$ and $\xi_j^E > 0$ denote the interference power threshold (IPT) of IDR k and EHR j , respectively, and $P_i^I > 0$ is the transmit power budget associated with the precoding vector \mathbf{w}_i , which can be fixed based on the transmit sum-power budget $P_{\max} > 0$, e.g., $P_i^I = P = P_{\max}/K$.

Similarly, the problem of optimizing \mathbf{v}_j is formulated accordingly as follows:

$$(P2): \max_{\{\mathbf{v}_j\}} \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{v}_j \quad (10a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{R}_k \mathbf{v}_j \leq \xi_k^I, \quad (10b)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{C}_n \mathbf{v}_j \geq \xi_n^E, \quad j \neq n, \quad (10c)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{v}_j \leq P_j^E, \quad (10d)$$

where we can fix $P_j^E = P = P_{\max}/K$.

2) *Problem II*: By dropping the interference-power constraints of the EHRs from (P1) and (P2), we respectively convert these problems to

$$(P3): \max_{\{\mathbf{w}_i\}} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{w}_i \quad \text{s.t. Eqs. (9b), (9d)} \quad (11)$$

and

$$(P4): \max_{\{\mathbf{v}_j\}} \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{v}_j \quad \text{s.t. Eqs. (10b), (10d)}. \quad (12)$$

3) *Problem III*: Then, we penalize the cost function in problems (P3) and (P4) by the interference induced to the IDRs, thus respectively reducing these optimization problems to

$$(P5): \max_{\{\mathbf{w}_i\}} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \left(\mathbf{R}_i - \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \mathbf{R}_k \right) \mathbf{w}_i \quad (13a)$$

$$\text{s.t. Eqs. (9b), (9d),} \quad (13b)$$

and

$$(P6): \max_{\{\mathbf{v}_j\}} \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \left(\mathbf{C}_j - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{R}_i \right) \mathbf{v}_j \quad (14a)$$

$$\text{s.t. Eqs. (10b), (10d).} \quad (14b)$$

B. SDR-based Designs

The above problems correspond to non-convex quadratically-constrained quadratic programs (QCQP). In order to tackle them, we employ the SDR method to convert them in convex semi-definite programs (SDP) which can be solved in polynomial time by convex optimization software that utilizes interior-point methods such as CVX [12]. To this end, we introduce the rank-one positive semi-definite (PSD) matrices $\mathbf{W}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ and $\mathbf{V}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ defined as $\mathbf{W}_i \triangleq \mathbf{w}_i \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger$ and $\mathbf{V}_j \triangleq \mathbf{v}_j \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger$ and drop the non-convex rank constraint. It is trivially proven that the considered SDRs are tight [13]. Hence, we can recover the optimal beamforming vectors from the solutions via eigenvalue decomposition. Next, we present the SDRs under study.

1) *SDR-based Design I*: Problem (P1) becomes:

$$(P7): \max_{\{\mathbf{W}_i\}} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_i) \quad (15a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_k \mathbf{W}_i) \leq \xi_k^I, \quad i \neq k, \quad (15b)$$

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{W}_i) \geq \xi_j^E, \quad (15c)$$

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{W}_i) \leq P_i^I, \quad (15d)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_i \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (15e)$$

Likewise, problem (P2) is converted to:

$$(P8): \max_{\{\mathbf{V}_j\}} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{V}_j) \quad (16a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_k \mathbf{V}_j) \leq \xi_k^I, \quad (16b)$$

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{C}_n \mathbf{V}_j) \geq \xi_n^E, \quad j \neq n, \quad (16c)$$

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{V}_j) \leq P_j^E, \quad (16d)$$

$$\mathbf{V}_j \succeq \mathbf{0}. \quad (16e)$$

2) *SDR-based Design II*: Problem (P3) is converted to:

$$(P9): \max_{\{\mathbf{W}_i\}} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{W}_i) \quad \text{s.t. Eqs. (15b), (15d), (15e)}. \quad (17)$$

Problem (P4), in turn, is transformed into:

$$(P10): \max_{\{\mathbf{V}_j\}} \text{Tr}(\mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{V}_j) \quad \text{s.t. Eqs. (16b), (16d), (16e)}. \quad (18)$$

3) *SDR-based Design III*: Finally, problem (P5) becomes:

$$(P11): \max_{\{\mathbf{W}_i\}} \text{Tr} \left(\left(\mathbf{R}_i - \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \mathbf{R}_k \right) \mathbf{W}_i \right) \quad (19a)$$

$$\text{s.t. Eqs. (15b), (15d), (15e).} \quad (19b)$$

Similarly, problem (P6) becomes:

$$(P12): \max_{\{\mathbf{V}_j\}} \text{Tr} \left(\left(\mathbf{C}_j - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{R}_i \right) \mathbf{V}_j \right) \quad (20a)$$

$$\text{s.t. Eqs. (16b), (16d), (16e).} \quad (20b)$$

C. Rayleigh Quotient-based Precoding Designs

The high computational complexity of SDR-based algorithms discourages their practical application. In this section, we present a low-complexity alternative. Specifically, we notice that the formulations of problems II and III have interference constraints associated with the IDRs and a transmit power constraint. We replace each interference power–transmit power constraints pair in the above problems with a single *tighter* constraint by utilizing the following harmonic mean inequality: $\left(\sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \frac{1}{x_r}\right)^{-1} \leq \min\{x_1, \dots, x_R\}$, $\mathcal{R} \triangleq \{1, \dots, R\}$. The applied HMR transforms the respective optimization problems into the optimization of a Rayleigh quotient, which is inherently connected to the generalized eigenvalue problem. In the following, we assume for convenience and without loss of generality that $P_i^I = P_j^E = P$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_E$.

1) *Rayleigh Quotient-based Design I*: Based on the above, we can relax problem (P3) as follows:

$$(P13): \max_{\{\mathbf{w}_i\}} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{w}_i \quad (21a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \left(\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \frac{P}{\xi_k^I} \mathbf{R}_k + \mathbf{I}_M \right) \mathbf{w}_i = P. \quad (21b)$$

(P13) corresponds to the generalized eigenvalue problem:

$$\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{w}_i = \mu \left(\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \frac{P}{\xi_k^I} \mathbf{R}_k + \mathbf{I}_M \right) \mathbf{w}_i, \quad (22)$$

where μ denotes the Lagrangian multiplier associated to the constraint in Eq. (21b). Thus, the solution to the relaxed problem (P13), \mathbf{w}_i^* , is the generalized eigenvector associated to the maximum generalized eigenvalue of the matrix pair $(\mathbf{A}_i, \mathbf{B}_k)$, where $\mathbf{A}_i = \mathbf{R}_i$ and $\mathbf{B}_k = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \frac{P}{\xi_k^I} \mathbf{R}_k + \mathbf{I}_M$. In the special case where $\xi_k^I = \xi_I, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_I, k \neq i$, we have $\mathbf{B}_k = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \mathbf{R}_k + \frac{\xi_I}{P} \mathbf{I}_M$.

Using a similar approach in problem (P4), \mathbf{v}_j^* is given by the generalized eigenvector associated to the maximum generalized eigenvalue of the matrix pair $(\mathbf{A}_j, \mathbf{B}_i)$, where $\mathbf{A}_j = \mathbf{C}_j$ and $\mathbf{B}_i = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \frac{P}{\xi_i^I} \mathbf{R}_i + \mathbf{I}_M$ or, in the special case where $\xi_i^I = \xi_I, \forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I$, $\mathbf{B}_i = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{R}_i + \frac{\xi_I}{P} \mathbf{I}_M$.

2) *Rayleigh Quotient-based Design II*: Likewise for problem (P5), we have the matrix pair $(\mathbf{A}_{i,k}, \mathbf{B}_i)$, where $\mathbf{A}_{i,k} = \mathbf{R}_i - \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \mathbf{R}_k$ and $\mathbf{B}_i = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \frac{P}{\xi_i^I} \mathbf{R}_i + \mathbf{I}_M$ or $\mathbf{B}_i = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{R}_i + \frac{\xi_I}{P} \mathbf{I}_M$ if $\xi_i^I = \xi_I, \forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I$.

Finally, for problem (P6), we have the matrix pair $(\mathbf{A}_{j,i}, \mathbf{B}_i)$, where $\mathbf{A}_{j,i} = \mathbf{C}_j - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{R}_i$ and $\mathbf{B}_i = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \frac{P}{\xi_i^I} \mathbf{R}_i + \mathbf{I}_M$ or $\mathbf{B}_i = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{R}_i + \frac{\xi_I}{P} \mathbf{I}_M$ if $\xi_i^I = \xi_I, \forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I$.

3) *Connection to SLNR-MAX Precoding*: The SLNR of IDR i and EHR j is defined as:

$$\text{SLNR}_i^I = \frac{\mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \left(\mathbf{R}_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{C}_j \right) \mathbf{w}_i}{\mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \left(\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \mathbf{R}_k \right) \mathbf{w}_i + \sigma_i^2}, \quad (23a)$$

$$\text{SLNR}_j^E = \frac{\mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \left(\sum_{n \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{C}_n \right) \mathbf{v}_j}{\mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{R}_i \right) \mathbf{v}_j + \delta_j^2}. \quad (23b)$$

Therefore, the SLNR-MAX information precoding vector assigned to IDR i corresponds to the generalized eigenvector associated with the maximum generalized eigenvalue of the matrix pair $(\mathbf{S}_{i,j}, \mathbf{Q}_{k,i})$, where $\mathbf{S}_{i,j} = \mathbf{R}_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{C}_j$ and $\mathbf{Q}_{k,i} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_I \setminus i} \mathbf{R}_k + \sigma_i^2 \mathbf{I}_M$. This is identical to the solution of the following modified version of problem (P5):

$$(P14): \max_{\{\mathbf{w}_i\}} \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \left(\mathbf{R}_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{C}_j \right) \mathbf{w}_i \quad (24a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \text{C5: } \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{R}_k \mathbf{w}_i \leq \xi_k^I, k \neq i, \text{ C2: } \mathbf{w}_i^\dagger \mathbf{w}_i \leq P_i^I, \quad (24b)$$

for the special case where $\xi_k^I = \xi_I, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}_I, k \neq i$, and $P_i^I = P, \forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I$, with the only difference that the regularization parameter is $\alpha_i = \sigma_i^2$ instead of $\alpha = \xi_I/P$. Similarly, the SLNR-MAX energy precoding vector assigned to EHR j corresponds to the generalized eigenvector associated with the maximum generalized eigenvalue of the matrix pair $(\mathbf{S}_j, \mathbf{Q}_{i,j})$, where $\mathbf{S}_j = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{C}_j$ and $\mathbf{Q}_{i,j} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}_I} \mathbf{R}_i + \delta_j^2 \mathbf{I}_M$. This is identical to the solution of the following modified version of problem (P6):

$$(P15): \max_{\{\mathbf{v}_j\}} \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \sum_{n \in \mathcal{K}_E} \mathbf{C}_n \mathbf{v}_j \quad (25a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \text{C6: } \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{v}_j \leq \xi_i^I, \text{ C4: } \mathbf{v}_j^\dagger \mathbf{v}_j \leq P_j^E, \quad (25b)$$

for the special case where $\xi_i^I = \xi_I, \forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I$, and $P_j^E = P, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_E$, with the only difference that the regularization parameter is $\alpha_j = \delta_j^2$ instead of $\alpha = \xi_I/P$.

D. Hybrid A/D Precoding

Let's assume that the BS adopts a fully-connected A/D architecture. The effective channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times M}$ is defined as $\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} \triangleq [\mathbf{h}_1, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{K_I}, \mathbf{g}_1, \dots, \mathbf{g}_{K_E}]^\dagger$ and has an SVD $\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{Z}^\dagger$, where the unitary matrix $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ holds the right singular vectors of \mathbf{H}_{eff} , $\mathbf{Z} = [\mathbf{z}_1, \dots, \mathbf{z}_{L-1}, \mathbf{z}_L, \mathbf{z}_{L+1}, \dots, \mathbf{z}_M]$. Then, we define $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times L}$, $\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{y}_1, \dots, \mathbf{y}_L]$, $\mathbf{y}_l \in \mathbb{C}^M, l \in \mathcal{L}$, as $\mathbf{Y} \triangleq \mathbf{Z}(:, 1:L)$, such that $\mathbf{y}_l = \mathbf{z}_l$. Finally, we set the phase shifts of the analog RFP as $\varphi_{m,l} = \angle \mathbf{y}_l(m), m \in \mathcal{M}$. After fixing \mathbf{F}_R , we can compute the DB information and energy precoding vectors by substituting $\mathbf{w}_i = \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_i$ and $\mathbf{v}_j = \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{t}_j$ in the problem formulations (P1)–(P6) and the corresponding SDR- and HMR-based problem formulations and solutions. Alternatively, we can minimize the Euclidean distance of the optimal FDP of each problem (I–III) $\mathbf{W}_* \triangleq [\mathbf{w}_1^*, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{K_I}^*, \mathbf{v}_1^*, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{K_E}^*]$ computed earlier from the HP $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{F}_B$. This results in an unconstrained least squares problem formulation:

$$(P16): \min_{\mathbf{F}_B} \|\mathbf{W}_* - \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{F}_B\|_F^2. \quad (26)$$

Consequently, the computation of the DBP requires essentially only matrix inversion and multiplication operations:

$$\mathbf{F}_B = \mathbf{F}_R^\dagger \left(\mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{F}_R^\dagger \right)^{-1} \mathbf{W}_*. \quad (27)$$

(a) Average data rate vs. angular user separation.

(b) Average harvested power vs. angular user separation.

Fig. 3. Performance of SDR- and HMR-based designs for varying angular user separation under $\xi = -5$ dB.

(a) Average data rate vs. angular user separation.

(b) Average harvested power vs. angular user separation.

Fig. 4. Performance of HMR-based designs vs. precoding heuristics for varying angular user separation under $\xi = 0$ dB.

IV. NUMERICAL EVALUATIONS

In this section, we comparatively evaluate the performance of the proposed linear precoding designs based on harmonic mean relaxation versus the one achieved by the proposed SDR-based linear precoding schemes and benchmark linear precoding heuristics. We assume $M = 5$; $K_I = K_E = 2$; $\kappa = 10$ dB; $\beta(d) = 10^{(-30+25 \log_{10}(d))/10}$, where d represents the propagation distance; $\sigma_i^2 = \delta_j^2 = -90$ dBm, $P_i^I = P_j^E = P = 1$ W, and $\xi_i^I = \xi_j^E = \xi$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{K}_I, j \in \mathcal{K}_E$. We consider a scenario where the EHRs and the IDRs are randomly placed on circles with center the BS and a radius of $r_E = 5$ m or $r_I = 10$ m, respectively. The numerical results are averages obtained after 1000 Monte Carlo simulation runs.

In Fig. 3, we plot the achieved average data rate of the IDRs and harvested power of the EHRs when SDR- or HMR-based designs are applied versus the angular user separation under $\xi = -5$ dB. We observe the following: i) The proposed low-complexity HMR designs achieve better performance in terms of both data rate and harvested power than the SDR-based ones, thanks to the tighter constraint which better balances

the requirements for protection from harmful interference and high received signal power. The data rate (harvested power) gains are greater for larger (smaller) angular user separation, due to the lower interference levels. ii) HMR II design, which balances the conflicting received signal power maximization and interference suppression objectives through penalization, performs slightly better than the HMR I design. Likewise, SDR III performs slightly better than the other SDR-based variants for the same reason, whereas SDR I performs slightly worse than SDR II since it has to meet an extra constraint.

In Fig. 4, we compare the HMR-based designs with linear precoding heuristics under a less stringent IPT value of $\xi = 0$ dB. We make the following observations: i) The proposed HMR-based designs substantially outperform these heuristics, which perform worse than the SDR-based designs under $\xi = -5$ dB. ii) The performance of the HMR-based designs is slightly improved for this less stringent IPT value. iii) MR/ZF and SLNR-MAX present the best performance in terms of data rate and harvested power, respectively, while RZF provides the worst performance in both cases. The trends of the MR/ZF and

Fig. 5. Average data rate vs. number of antennas in a massive MIMO network.

Fig. 6. Average harvested power: FD vs. HP designs.

RZF curves depend on the effect of the angular user separation to the ZF component of these schemes.

These tests demonstrate the robustness of the proposed HMR designs to angular user separation and, therefore, their insensitivity with respect to the applied user selection policy in this regard. We should also mention that the presented flexible (in terms of the defined IPT) HMR-based designs do not require demanding computations of combining coefficients, as in the case of MR/ZF precoding.

Fig. 5 considers a massive MIMO network with varying number of antennas per BS. We see that the HMR I scheme achieves higher data rate than the standard precoding heuristics, thanks to its inherent capability in dealing with interference. Naturally, the performance of all methods improves with the number of antennas and the performance gap closes. While so far we solely focused on FD implementations, in Fig. 6 we consider the extreme case of an A/D BS with $L = 4$ and $M = 6$ under $\xi = -5$ dB. We notice that we achieve degraded SDR- and HMR-based performance in comparison to the FD implementation, due the limitations in the number of RF chains and antennas and also because of the SVD-based RFP heuristic, yet we harvest a sufficient amount of power.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed flexible interference-constrained precoding designs for SWIPT that admit closed-form solutions. Numerical simulation results highlighted the performance gains of these low-complexity schemes against benchmarks in various setups and provided valuable insights. In the future, we plan to study the applicability of these designs in the context of near-field beam focusing for SWIPT.

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